

RESORCINOL SUCCINEIN AND ITS BROMO DERIVATIVES AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS

By RAM CHARAN MEHROTRA

The behaviour of resorcinol succinein as an adsorption indicator in mixed halide solutions has been described. The applicability of two more dyes, dibromo- and tetrabromo- resorcinol succinein as adsorption indicators has been investigated. They have been found to be very suitable indicators for the titration of bromide, iodide and thiocyanate ions.

In a recent communication (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 166), the applicability of resorcinol succinein as adsorption indicator to the argentometric titration of halide ions has been described. The present communication describes the use of resorcinol succinein as adsorption indicator in the mixed halide solutions and also of the dibromo and tetrabromo derivatives of the dye in argentometric titrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Dyes.—The resorcinol succinein was prepared by the method recently described by Sheshadri and co-workers (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 26A, .99). The resorcinol succinein thus prepared had a melting point of 256°. The dye employed in the investigations previously published (*loc. cit.*) was prepared by the method of Biggs and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2934) and had the melting point 234°. However, on the repetition of the work with the purer dye, no detectable difference was found from the data already published. It appears that the slight impurities present in the resorcinol succinein by the method of Biggs and Pope are not of such a nature as to affect the adsorbability of the dye on the silver halide particles.

Dibromo and tetrabromo derivatives of the dye were prepared by the bromination of the succinein in glacial acetic acid (Sheshadri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The recrystallised dibromo derivative had the melting point 246° and the tetrabromo product decomposed above 300°.

0.2% Solutions of these dyes were prepared in 50% alcohol and these solutions were used as indicators throughout these investigations.

Resorcinol succinein as Adsorption Indicator.—It has been described that using resorcinol succinein as adsorption indicator, chloride ions can be titrated satisfactorily up to a dilution of $N/50$; in the case of thiocyanate ions, the indicator marks the end-point sharply up to a dilution of $N/100$, in the case of bromide, up to a dilution of $N/200$, and in the case of iodide ions, solutions as dilute as $N/4000$ may be titrated within 0.5% accuracy. It was considered of interest to study the behaviour of the indicator in mixed halide solutions.

Belladen and Piazza (*Ann. Chim. Appl.*, 1932, 22, 631) find that although Brilliant Archill C and Chromotrope F4B are suitable indicators for all the chloride, bromide and iodide ions separately, yet when a mixture of iodide and chloride ions is titrated against silver ions, the end-point (pink→grey green) occurs, when silver nitrate equivalent to only the iodide ions present has been added. Resorcinol succinein is also quite suitable an indicator for all the three halide ions ; yet in contrast to the above indicators, it resembles the ordinary indicator fluorescein in marking the end-point when the total of all the halide ions present has been precipitated.

However, the useful range of the indicator can be increased in mixed halide solutions. Chloride and bromide ions alone do not give sharp end-points when they are present in dilutions greater than $N/50$ and $N/200$ respectively. As the following tables will show, in the presence of iodide ions the chloride and bromide ions can be titrated with very sharp end-points up to dilutions of $N/200$ and $N/500$ respectively.

TABLE I

Vol. and conc. of halide soln.	Drop of indicator.	Vol. and conc. of AgNO_3 soln.	Transition of colour.	Remarks.
10 c.c. of $N/200$ -KCl+10 c.c. of $N/200$ -KI	2	20.05 c.c. of $N/200$ - AgNO_3	Light pink susp.→ deep pink ppt.	The coagulation occurs just at the end-point with the transference of light pink colour from the suspension to a deep pink colour on ppt.
10 c.c. of $N/500$ -KBr+ 10 c.c. of $N/500$ -KI	2	20.02 c.c. of $N/500$ - AgNO_3	Yellow susp.→ pink susp.	The colour change occurs sharply in the suspension phase, followed by coagulation occurring in a few seconds when pink coloured ppt. separates. Quite reversible to both KBr and KI.
10 c.c. of $N/100$ -KCl+10 c.c. of $N/100$ -KBr	1	20.05 c.c. of $N/100$ - AgNO_3	Pale yellow susp.→ pink susp.	Very sharp end-point. Quite sharp with respect to both KCl or KBr.
5 c.c. of $N/100$ -KI+5 c.c. of $N/100$ -KCNS	1	10 to 10.02 c.c. of $N/100$ - AgNO_3	Yellow susp.→ pink susp.	Sharp colour change in the homogeneous phase. Reversible to both potassium iodide as well as thiocyanate.

Dibromoresorcinol succinein as Adsorption Indicator.—Like the corresponding dyes from phthalic acid, dibromo derivative shows greater adsorbability than the resorcinol succinein itself. The greater adsorbability of the dye renders it unsuitable for the titration of chloride ions either in the neutral or acidic media. It, however, gives very sharp end-points in the case of bromide, thiocyanate and iodide ions and with its aid titrations are possible in acidic media, whereas the resorcinol succinein does not mark the end point in media of p_H lower than 7. However, none of the halide ions mark the end-point in the ammoniacal medium, and when mixtures of iodide and chloride ions are titrated, the end-point occurs when the total of the halide ions present has been precipitated and not at the point when only the iodide ions present have been titrated.

TABLE II

Vol. and conc. of halide soln.	Drops of indicator	Vol. and conc. of AgNO_3 soln.	Transition of colour.	Remarks.
10 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KCl}$	2	10 to 10.02 c.c. of $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$	Orange susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs at the end-point with the transference of colour from the suspension to ppt. However, the change of colour is not at all marked. If the chloride solution is acidified, the coagulation and adsorption of the colour on ppt. occur much before the equivalent point.
10 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KBr}$	2	"	Pale orange susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	Coagulation just at the equivalent point with the transference of and a sharp change in the shade of colour. The end-point is sharp and reversible.
10 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KBr} + 4$ c.c. of $N\text{-HAc}$.	2	"	Yellow susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	The end-point is sharp. The coagulation occurs with half a drop more of silver nitrate.
10 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KI}$	3	"	Yellow susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	The coagulation occurs just a little before the equivalent point. The colour change occurs on the coagulated particles and is quite reversible. Titration is possible in presence of acetic acid. The end-point does not appear in ammoniacal solution.
10 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KCNS}$	2	9.98 to 10.02 c.c. of $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$	Orange susp. \rightarrow deep pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs much earlier and the particles take up a slight pinkish tinge; at the equivalent point, a sharp colour change occurs with the transference of colour from the suspension to the ppt. The titration is possible in acidic solutions.

Tetrabromoresorcinol succinein as Adsorption Indicator.—Tetrabromo derivative of resorcinol succinein shows even a greater adsorbability than the dibromo derivative. However, on account of the loading in the molecule, the colour changes occurring at adsorption and desorption are not so sharp as in the case of non-brominated dye or its dibromo derivative. With the help of the dye, titration of bromide, iodide and thiocyanate ions can be carried out in neutral or acidic media. Iodide ions alone can be titrated in ammoniacal medium also and in the presence of dilute ammonia or ammonium carbonate; iodide ions alone can be titrated in the presence of chloride ions, when the chloride ions present are less than half the concentration of the iodide ions.

TABLE III

Vol. and conc. of halide soln.	Drops of indicator.	Vol. and conc. of AgNO_3 soln.	Transition of colour.	Remarks.
5 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KI}$	2	4.98 to 5.01 c.c. of $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$	Pink susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	Coagulation begins quite early, but the particles remain yellow. The titration is quite reversible.
5 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KI} + 3$ to 4 c.c. of $N\text{-HAc}$.	3	5 to 5.02 c.c. of $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$	Yellow susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	The end-point is very sharp and quite reversible. The coagulation occurs just at the equivalent point.

TABLE III (contd.)

5 c.c. of N/10-KI + 0.1g. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$	2	4.98 to 5.0 c.c. of N/10- AgNO_3	Yellow ppt. \rightarrow pink ppt.	The coagulation begins from the beginning, but the particles remain yellow. About 0.5% before the equivalent point, the particles assume a pinkish shade, but the suspension becomes clear just at the equivalent point with deepening of colour of the particles.
Above + 2.5 c.c. N/10-KCl	2	" "	" "	" "
5 c.c. of N/10-KBr	2	5 to 5.02 c.c. of N/10- AgNO_3	Pink susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	The colour change at the end-point is not marked; the colour is merely transferred from suspension to the precipitate.
5 c.c. of N/10-KBr + 2 c.c. of N-HAc	3	5 to 5.01 c.c. of N/10- AgNO_3	White susp. \rightarrow pink ppt.	Coagulation occurs just at the end-point. The end-point is very sharp.
5 c.c. of N/10-KCNS	2	4.98 to 5 c.c. of N/10- AgNO_3	Orange susp \rightarrow pink ppt.	Coagulation much earlier; particles take up slight colour before the end-point. The end-point is much sharper in the presence of acetic acid, in which case, the particles remain colorless up to the end-point.
5 c.c. of N/10-KI + 2.5 c.c. of N/10-KCl + 0.1g. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ or 1 c.c. of N- NH_4OH	2	4.98 to 5.0 c.c. of N/10- AgNO_3	Yellow ppt. \rightarrow pink ppt.	The coagulation begins quite early, but the particles remain yellow.
5 c.c. of N/10-KCl				The adsorption of the dye and the colour change occurs much before the end-point. The titration is not possible in neutral or acidic medium.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
THE UNIVERSITY, ALLAHABAD.

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